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FAMILY INVOLVEMENT IN SCHOOL: BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

This study addressed the relationship between neuroscience and literacy, with the aim of understanding the brain processes involved in learning to read and write. Using a literature review approach, relevant studies published in the last ten years were selected. The analysis of the results revealed the importance of phonological skills, the dual-route model and neural plasticity in this process. The results highlighted the need for teachers to be familiar with neuroscientific knowledge to improve their educational practices. Incorporating these contributions can improve academic performance and promote more effective pedagogical strategies in literacy.

KEYWORDS: neuroscience, literacy, brain processes.